

ABSTRACT

HOW IS THE HISTORY OF NORTHERN CYPRUS REFLECTED IN ITS ENGLISH LANGUAGE PRACTICE?

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Cyprus, an island with a splendid history, has been shaped by numerous rulers, including the Greeks, Assyrians, Romans, Byzantines, and primarily the British Empire from 1878 to 1960. The research investigated the historical elements that have shaped English language education in Northern Cyprus, a region significantly influenced by its colonial history under British rule, as well as the socio-political fragmentation that followed the events of 1974. The study aimed to fill the gap in empirical research regarding the connections between historical contexts, cultural identity, and language education, particularly in a state where Turkish is the official language, while English plays a vital role in educational and professional development. Applying a mixed-methods approach that combines archival research, surveys, and interviews, the study highlights the substantial effects of colonial legacies and current political divisions on English language teaching and societal attitudes. The results reveal that English language education in Northern Cyprus is inextricably tied to its colonial past, affecting not only the development of curricula and teaching methods but also public perceptions of the language. Participants in the research called for a revision of the educational curriculum, stressing the importance of adopting more communicative and immersive teaching strategies instead of focusing excessively on grammatical precision. This study emphasises the importance of recognising historical influences in contemporary English language education practices. Ultimately, it argues that a more responsive educational framework, attuned to the changing linguistic and socio-political environment, is crucial for adequately preparing learners in Northern Cyprus to meet the challenges of global communication and progress.

Keywords: British Administration's colonial history, Curriculum development, English language education, English Language Teaching Methods, Global communication, Historical Impact on ELT, Northern Cyprus.